

1 **Therapeutic targeting in lung cancer for the treatment of lymph node metastasis: TNFRSF25 and**
2 **TNFSF15.**

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7 The high rate of brain metastasis in patients with non-small cell and small cell lung cancer demands
8 discovery of novel therapeutic targets to treat lymph node metastasis which serves as an intermediate to
9 the CNS (central nervous system) (1-5). We recently utilized whole transcriptome technologies to define
10 the full complement of differentially expressed kinases and phosphatases in HER2+ breast cancer: in the
11 primary tumor, and in metastasis to the CNS (6-8). Here we utilize whole transcriptome technologies (9,
12 10) to measure total transcription in the lymph node metastases of humans with small cell and non-small
13 cell lung cancer. We describe here a pair of therapeutic targets that is up-regulated and differentially
14 expressed in lymph node metastasis in humans with small cell and non-small cell lung cancer, *TNFRSF25*
15 and *TNFSF15*, as candidate therapeutic targets for the medical management of lymph node metastasis in
16 human lung cancer.
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We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the lymph nodes to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the lymph node metastatic transcriptome in small cell and non-small cell lung cancer: a pair of therapeutic targets that is up-regulated and metastasis-specific, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy: TNFRSF25 and TNFSF15.

Results

Figure 1: TNFRSF25 and TNFSF15 are differentially expressed in lymph node metastasis in humans with lung cancer..

I. Lymph node metastases and primary tumors from humans with non-small cell lung cancer.

n=2 primary tumors from humans with non-small cell lung cancer

n=2 lymph node metastases (tumor) from humans with non-small cell lung cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
8718	2.41E-01	0.703	-1.1734227	-0.8249445	609.7	TNFRSF25	2797/20667	86.4
9966	6.60E-02	0.751	-1.838427	-1.3807705	110.38	TNFSF15	1463/20667	92.9

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the lung and in lymph node metastases of humans with non-small cell lung cancer (5), we discovered differential expression of tumor necrosis factor receptor superfamily, member 25 and tumor necrosis factor (ligand) superfamily, member 15, encoded by *TNFRSF25* and *TNFSF15*, respectively, in metastasis to the lymph nodes in humans with NSCLC (**Chart 1**). The expression of TNFRSF25 and TNFSF15 changed more than 85% and 90% of the human NSCLC lymph node metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 20,667 transcripts ("Rank"), respectively. Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of TNFRSF25 and TNFSF15 messenger RNA in NSCLC lymph node metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of TNFRSF25 and TNFSF15 during NSCLC disease progression.

II. Lymph node metastases and primary tumors from humans with small cell lung cancer.

n=2 primary tumors from humans with small cell lung cancer

n=4 lymph node metastases (tumor) from humans with small cell lung cancer

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
A_33_P3234530	4.02E-03	-3.9	-1.72176	-3.03983945	TNFRSF25	1234/58341	97.9
A_23_P94754	1.21E-01	-1.72	-4.97688	-1.86722286	TNFSF15	11543/58341	80.2

Through measurement of total transcription in the lymph node metastases of humans with small cell lung cancer as compared to primary tumors of the lung, we validated differential expression of TNFRSF25 and TNFSF15 in SCLC lymph node metastasis in humans (**Chart 2**). The expression of TNFRSF25 and TNFSF15 here changed more than 97% and 80% of the lymph node metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 58,341 transcripts ("Rank"),

1 respectively. Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of TNFRSF25 and TNFSF15
2 messenger RNA in lymph node metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of TNFRSF25 and TNFSF15
3 during disease progression and metastasis in humans with lung cancer.

4 Thus, differential and increased expression of TNFRSF25 and TNFSF15 defines the lymph node
5 metastatic transcriptome in human lung cancer.

6 **Discussion**

7 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
8 treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like
9 trastuzumab). Inhibitors of TNFRSF25 and TNFSF15, once evaluated for toxicity and safety, can
10 immediately be tested for efficacy in patients with lymph node metastasis who have failed previous
11 treatment, with the goal of identifying the most effective inhibitors of lymph node metastasis in humans
12 with lung cancer. A multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP
13 synthesis, replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, and target *CDKN*
14 inactivation and ATP-binding cassette pump expression in resistant cases, is most likely to be most
15 effective in limiting tumor clone resistance (11).
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Methods

We utilized GSE235634 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the lymph nodes and in primary tumors from humans with lung cancer (along with GSE162102 for target validation) using RNA-sequencing and microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods.